

D6.2 – First Communication and Dissemination Plan

Work Package 6 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Task 6.1 - Communication and Dissemination

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
OA	Open Access
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document aims to provide a comprehensive plan to deploy InterSTORE's Communication and Dissemination activities with the final scope of maximising the impact of the project results.

In the context of the InterSTORE project, the Communication and Dissemination activities play a crucial role since they intend to promote the divulgation of the project's activities and outcomes to civil society, stakeholders, suppliers and authorities with the aim to reach a wider audience, facilitate the transfer of technology and accelerate the implementation of the project's results and findings. Thanks to these activities, which are the core of the WP6 of the project, it will be possible to provide the visibility of the objectives achieved and thus obtain a broader scientific and socio-economic impact.

To ensure the effective success of InterSTORE's Communication and Dissemination activities, this plan is aimed at setting up the guidelines and the performance indicators which will result indispensable to implementing and verifying the Communications and Dissemination actions throughout the duration as well as after the end of the project. The present document represents the first InterSTORE's Communication and Dissemination plan, whereas a second and final plan will be developed before the end of the project reporting on the dissemination activities that will be put into place to further maximize the impact of the project's results after its end.

Going into the details of this plan, it aims at identifying the strategy that will be implemented with the main objective of increasing the visibility and impact of the project and its results by facilitating the transfer of knowledge and technology. In identifying the strategy devised for InterSTORE, a privileged place is reserved for identifying target groups, as this is fundamental for choosing the most appropriate means to reach them.

The tools that have been selected to better spread the message of InterSTORE to its eight targeted groups are carefully illustrated and include an elaborate visual identity, useful to make the project distinctive and well recognizable, and the creation of a website, accessible by anyone and anywhere showing the progress of the project, including upcoming events and publications. Together with the website, the Social Media channels LinkedIn and Twitter have been created to increase the visibility of the project and promote its activities to a wide audience. The elaboration of a newsletter, communication materials, and scientific publications have also been foreseen as other important means to reach the targeted audience. Active participation and organization of workshops, webinars and events will open a new set of opportunities in dissemination of the project and its results.

The InterSTORE's partners, following the internal coordination procedures detailed below in the document, are responsible for the carrying out of InterSTORE's communication and dissemination activities, as well as for the assessment of it. A set of 11 Key Performance Indicators was identified for this purpose, including the number of attendees of the events and the views on social media and websites, to monitor and adjust the means here identified.

To prevent any misunderstanding, for the purpose of this document the terms “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation” are intended as defined in the presentation released by the European Commission¹.

Nevertheless, this plan will only focus on the Communication and Dissemination activities. The Exploitation activity is not here contemplated since it will be covered in D6.3 entitled “First draft of the Exploitation Strategy, Plan and IPR report” and in D6.4 entitled “Final Exploitation Roadmap including Business Plan and IPR report”.

¹ Find here the definitions of “Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation”: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-08/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf.

1. GOALS, OBJECTIVES AND STAKEHOLDERS

1.1. Communication and dissemination long-term goals and objectives

The overall aim of WP6 is to increase the visibility and impact of InterSTORE and its results through appropriate dissemination, communication and exploitation activities that will be undertaken from the real beginning of the project. The primary goal is to grow the ecosystem's size, scope and actions for increasing scientific and socio-economic impact and thus to foster public awareness and stakeholders' engagement during the project's lifetime and beyond.

The key objectives of the Communication and Dissemination activities within InterSTORE are:

- Maximizing the dissemination of the project's outcomes to stakeholders in industry, suppliers and authorities to speed up the deployment of the research findings;
- Fostering the dissemination of the results through presentations during webinars, technical conferences, and scientific publications;
- Facilitating the transfer of technology by accelerating the dissemination of the project activities and implementation of the project's results and findings to interested stakeholders with the final aim to promote their exploitation and the adoption of common standard;
- Engaging in Communication and Dissemination activities with similar projects and initiatives to create synergies and collaborations between EU-funded programme actions;
- Achieving good knowledge management including appropriate handling of IPR.

1.2. Communication and dissemination strategy

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities are embedded into WP6 that is led by EASE with the support of all the partners that share a great expertise in the divulgation and promotion of EU projects results. EASE carried out the elaboration of the present plan with the aim of answering the following points: Who (namely, who is considered to be the targeted audience); What (e.g. what are key messages that the consortium wants to communicate and spread); How (namely, what will be the communications channels/activities that will be used) and When (when these activities are planned).

The methodology used for the development of this plan was based on a simple model which takes into consideration a value to be disseminated, including target groups and key partners as knowledge sources. In the realization of the first C&D plan the following priorities have been considered:

- Identify the target group audiences, namely who will benefit from the InterSTORE economic and societal impacts and thus who are the final recipients of the project,
- Ensure that the message is clearly defined and addresses the needs of each target group, considering the necessity to keep them informed on project developments, boundaries and opportunities,

- Select/hone the dissemination/communication activities that are better tailored to transmit the promotion messages relating to InterSTORE results with a business-oriented as well as a societal character,
- Contribute to stakeholders working groups that could bring about cues and suggestions for policy recommendations.

The elaborated strategy focuses on the principle of 'Tell the InterSTORE story' to empower stakeholders and foster community engagement through InterSTORE initiatives. One key aspect of this strategy is to create opportunities for stakeholders to share their experiences and insights gained from their involvement in the InterSTORE project. Additionally, community engagement in each demo site will be a fundamental aspect of this strategy and it will generate a collaborative approach which will create a sense of inclusivity and foster a strong community bond, leading to a more sustainable and effective implementation of InterSTORE solutions. The consortium will prioritize places and channels where target audiences already gather on and offline to get more exposure. In addition to this, through the project SSH approach of the so-called "Triple layered business model canvas" (TLBMC), the societal, environmental and economic impacts of InterSTORE will be analysed and this exploration will serve as input on how to use and disseminate the project's data and results. With the purpose of maximising the impact of the InterSTORE, his Communication and Dissemination plan provides for a rolling delivery flow of relevant news and content pushed to multiple communications channels with a mix of textual and rational written material together with visual image/video supports.

1.3. Stakeholder groups and management

To optimize InterSTORE's value and ensure the publicity of the activities pursued and the goals achieved, the project's Communication and Dissemination activities are addressed to specific target groups, identified through an accurate analysis by the partners during the proposal phase. The identification of the target groups and the audience is functional to an appropriate and tailored choice of communication channels and tools to better disseminate the project's message and outcomes.

Considering that the aim of the innovative InterSTORE software is to enable the integration of decentralized energy storage solutions to the power grid to offer flexible services by connecting a multitude of energy market participants and aggregating their supply and demand functions, the InterSTORE project offers benefits to several stakeholders. The project not only provides technological advantages but also socio-economic benefits like the reduction of balancing costs. At the same time, it impacts the value chain of potentially new or already established market participants. Thus, the entire value chain, comprising the private and commercial prosumers, TSO, DSO, BRP, ESCO, energy traders, standardization bodies and business and academic research units jointly are involved in the project providing and benefiting from the flexibility service and by the adoption of a common communication standard

Therefore, all InterSTORE's stakeholders will be reached through specific tools, techniques, and languages appropriately selected that will ensure their constant involvement and engagement in the project as well as their deep awareness of InterSTORE's objectives set and results achieved.

1.3.1 Pilot Owner and HESS Asset owner, Energy suppliers, and System operators

InterSTORE consortium will actively engage 4 pilots and HESS assets owners, which are managed by project partners organization, and it will guarantee that they will capitalize on the project dissemination activities. As the project aims to support digital transition in the distributed energy storage sector so to improve energy efficiency and increase CO2 reduction

of Distributed Energy Resources, all energy system stakeholders, final users as well as scientific community and policy makers have been identified as an essential target audience to disseminate project results.

Grid operators (TSO/DSOs) and energy suppliers (ESCOs), who can exploit the developed technologies, as well as relevant players of the energy system, such as Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs), will be involved through workshops, webinars, conferences and events.

1.3.2 EV users and Energy Community, consumers and general public

InterSTORE consortium will assure that the final beneficiaries (energy communities' members, EV & Fleet owners, campus staff as well as laboratory employees) will be continuously involved and engaged. End users' feedback will be collected before and after the project implementation to assess the success of the project activities. The goal of InterSTORE, i.e. to give the European Energy Industry a guide to make easier the integration of the storage devices in systems, is aligned with the EC's Energy Package "Clean Energy for All Europeans", which aims to support European domestically-produced energy and reduce our reliance on foreign energy sources. The societal impacts of the project are therefore many, and they include resilience after the energy price crisis, the reduction of the skepticism about optimization of HESS, as well as socioeconomic benefits, such as reduced balancing and energy costs and an increased use of renewable energies. Due to the importance of Energy communities, energy cooperatives, consumers and the general public as part of the target groups for this C&D plan, accurate channels and tools have been selected to properly reach them.

1.3.3 EC and other initiatives

InterSTORE partners will assure to carry out cluster dissemination activities, thus disseminating the project result within the partnerships and networks they are involved with. Indeed, the project results will complement and generate links with other ongoing projects and initiatives, such as BRIDGE H2020 Smart Grids and Storage Cooperation Group, 2ZERO, INTERCONNECT, BD4NRG, BRIGHT, PLATONE. A proper dissemination action is therefore crucial to share with these initiatives InterSTORE's lessons learned and results.

1.3.4 Scientific Community

Academia and research centres will be engaged through participation in scientific congresses and research publications. InterSTORE will generate a significant amount of data, in particular in relation to the field test, strengthening research and innovation expertise regarding the two main project pillars: Interoperability and Flexibility of HESS integration. These scientific results will be spread through scientific publications, articles published in magazines, CORDIS news (EU community), and partners' newsletters and magazines. InterSTORE will fully support EC Open Access Strategy obligations, and the core of its view will be released as open source. Moreover, the link with open foundations such as Linux Foundation Energy will serve as another channel to distribute the knowledge related to new products and services.

1.3.5 Policymakers & Public Bodies

Policymakers and public bodies are another key element of InterSTORE's Communication and Dissemination activities. They will be reached through the release of white papers (addressed to at least 1 EU parliament and EU commissioner) as well as through the invitation to project events, especially the last event, to illustrate to them the project's outcomes and suggestions for future initiatives and regulations.

1.3.6 Inverter manufacturer

Inverter manufacturers are one of the main beneficiaries of InterSTORE project that will try to support their devices interoperability to assure new flexibility services. They will be reached starting from the devices manufacturer that are present in InterSTORE living labs and will be invited to sign a letter of support to be involved as IAB (Industrial Advisory Board member). Inverter manufacturer will be able to test few of the tools that InterSTORE will release on github and might receive the assistance by project partners.

1.3.7 Standardization communities

Standardization bodies will be reached with the support of VDE partner and a dedicated open call to select the certification organization that will verify the InterSTORE automatic testing tool to certify 2030.5 protocol fulfilment will be assured.

1.3.8 Open-Source community and Energy Linux Foundation

Linux Energy foundation is one of our critical stakeholders on which InterSTORE will reply the sustainability of most of the solution developed. Based on that the open IP licence that InterSTORE will be the same that LINUX foundation usually used (APACHE). InterSTORE will continuously present its results to Linux Energy foundation.

Table 1: Targeted audience and communication channels

Target Audience	Communication channels/ tools	Goals
Pilot Owner and HESS Asset owner, Energy suppliers, and System operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posters - brochures - e-newsletters - social networks - website - participation in workshops/webinars - participation in conferences and events - final meeting - Video 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobilise the sector's interest - Improve knowledge and know-how - Raise awareness - Disseminate project results
EV users, Energy Community, campus' employees consumers and general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posters - brochures - e-newsletters - social networks - website - participation in webinars - participation in conferences and events - final meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect end users' feedbacks - Raise awareness of technology and innovation - Raise awareness of the role of citizens and of public funding

	-Video	
EC and other initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posters - brochures - e-newsletters - social networks - website - participation in webinars - participation in conferences and events - final meeting -White paper connected to BRIDGE and BATTERY EUROPE WG -Video 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobilise the sector's interest - Foster cooperation - Raise awareness - Disseminate project findings and results
Scientific Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posters - brochures - e-newsletters - social networks - website - participation in workshops/webinars - participation in conferences and events - scientific publications - final meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve knowledge and know-how - Raise awareness - Provide synergies - Disseminate project findings and results
Polymakers & Public Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participation in conferences and events -White paper connected to BRIDGE and BATTERY EUROPE WG - final meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Influence policy priorities/raise awareness - Use InterSTORE's results for future policy-making and project funding
Inverter manufacturer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IAB engagement - Dedicated workshop and training course on the tool developed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enlarge InterSTORE IAB, assuring that the tools and UC tested are market driven -Increase the number of EU inverters manufacturers 2030.5 certified.

Standardization communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dedicated workshop - Open call - Connection to Australian and Canadian standardization communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identify an EU certification bodies that will certify InterSTORE testing tool for certifying 2030.5 devices -Improve connection between EU-Australia and Canada
Open-Source community and Energy Linux Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Webinars and conferences - GitHub repository 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assure sustainability and updates of the tool developed after the project end.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND RESOURCES

2.1 Visual identity

The visual identity of the project was established in March 2023 and was reported in Deliverable 6.1 “Report on project and website”. It plays a crucial role in establishing a recognizable and distinct brand image. It encompasses various elements that are carefully designed to align with the project's needs and the preferences of consortium partners. The key components of a visual identity typically include a logo, colour palette, typography, and secondary identity elements. A well-designed visual identity creates a cohesive and professional appearance, making it easier for stakeholders, partners, and the target audience to identify and engage with the project.

2.1.1 Logo

The logo of the InterSTORE project was elaborated by consortium partners during the preparation phase of the project. The logo was designed to reflect the project's overarching idea and its scope. As part of the visual identity development, the colours were carefully selected and edited to enhance the concept and represent the project effectively. The logo includes the acronym of the project, which stands for ‘Interoperable openN-source Tools to Enable hybRidisation, utiliSation, and moneTisation of stORage flexibility’. In addition, the logo incorporates cubes to symbolize the project's complexity and the combination of various elements required to develop a novel open-source software that facilitates interoperability. A project logo, together with colour scheme, typography, and icons can be found in the [Appendix A](#).

2.1.2 Colour Palette

Together with the logo, a colour palette was proposed by a subcontractor. Based on the feedback of the Consortium partners, the most popular variant was chosen, and it is represented in the following colours: Dark Blue, Blue Turquoise and Purple. Each colour carries its own symbolic meaning, contributing to the overall representation of the project's visual identity.

The Dark Blue colour represents power and responsibility, knowledge and reliability. It conveys a sense of authority and trustworthiness, aligning with the InterSTORE project's commitment to delivering reliable solutions and embodying expertise in the field of storage flexibility.

Blue Turquoise speaks for the electronic age and the world of computers, and communication on a large scale. The Turquoise is also a colour which represents, calmness and clarity, associated with the aim of the project to facilitate efficient communication and seamless integration of storage solutions.

The Purple colour signifies creativity and wisdom. It represents the InterSTORE project's innovative thinking and the aspiration to bring fresh ideas and insightful solutions to the domain.

2.1.3 Typography

To represent the InterSTORE project following three fonts were chosen:

1. Bahnschrift is the main font. It is meant to be utilized in templates and official documents;
2. Arial is used on printed materials, as well as in official documents;
3. N27 is used in graphics on Social Media and Website.

2.1.4 Secondary identity

Together with the primary identity, a secondary identity was developed to further enhance its visual representation. It includes different elements, such as icons and geometrical shapes in the corresponding colours of the project. These elements will be used in the design of the templates and printed materials.

2.1.5 Templates

To support Communication and Dissemination activities, different templates were created with the purpose to be used during the project's lifetime (see [Appendix B – Templates](#)):

1. Deliverable Template ([figure 9](#))
2. Letterhead ([figure 10](#));
3. Presentation ([figure 11](#));
4. Minutes of the Meeting ([figure 12](#));
5. Text ([figure 13](#)).

2.2 Use of EU flag and Disclaimer

As per Grant Agreement article 17.2, Communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (media relations, conferences, seminars, information materials, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media) must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate). InterSTORE's consortium is committed to respecting the given rules and implementing strong efforts in maximizing the visibility of EU support.

2.3 Project website

Nowadays, it is essential to have an online tool accessible from anywhere. With the widespread use of the internet and advancements in technology, people expect to have access to their tools, data, and information from any location and device. For this reason, the website of InterSTORE was developed, with the final aim to enhance the visibility of the project and its easy access from anyone and anywhere.

The website of the InterSTORE project was finalised in April 2023. It supports the project's visual identity and serves as a reference for a wide audience interested in learning about the project and the progress of its activities. It will communicate the overview of the project, detailed information about its objectives, news, event announcements, and publications of the partners of the project. The purpose of the website is to present, share, and display all the related information about the development of the project and disseminate its results.

As its core communication and dissemination channel, the website is accessible not only on desktop but also on mobile. It is user and mobile friendly, it works well on each device and adjusts to the smaller mobile sizes.

EASE is in charge of regularly updating the website with the project's progress, upcoming events, and news items. EASE will oversee updating it as needed and collecting the inputs and suggestions from the partners to have appropriate content about the project's development and the commitment of each partner.

2.3.1 Domain

The domain of the InterSTORE website is www.interstore-project.eu. The website was created on the platform WordPress, which gives a wide range of options to create a user-friendly interface and makes it accessible to visitors worldwide.

2.3.2 Sitemap

The figure of the sitemap, which can be found in the [Appendix D – Sitemap](#), shows a hierarchy of all the pages both parent and child one.

Parent pages are the landing page, as well as 'About', 'Use Cases', 'Living Labs', 'News & Events', 'Resources', 'Cluster Projects, and 'Contact Us' pages.

Child pages are 'InterSTORE project', 'Our partners', 9 Use Cases, 4 living labs, 'News of the project', and 'Upcoming & Passed Events'.

2.4 Social Media

Together with the website, Social Media channels LinkedIn and Twitter will be highly beneficial to increase the visibility of the project, promote its activities and maximise the dissemination of its results. The use of Social Media will help to reach the project's target audience and to spread the news about its ongoing and future activities and initiatives.

Social media channels are the instruments to interact and create a dialogue between communities and to connect with industry peers. They represent a unique way to obtain direct feedback and new information. Followers of Social Media channels will significantly enrich InterSTORE's communication by publishing images and videos, and thus contributing to the effort of the project's partners. Similarly, Social Media channels will be used as a bridge between users where they can discuss its objective and results and reach directly its audience. EASE will manage the Social Media accounts of the project and it will update it with the content provided by the partners.

Twitter profile: [InterSTORE_eu](#)

Twitter is an online platform where people communicate in short messages (280 characters). It is used for instant messaging for the promotion of the events and for live tweeting during the events. Through the use of Twitter, we will be able to display specific content related to the project. Formal partners of the project will be always tagged in posts, and this could help to increase the visibility of the company. Compared to LinkedIn, the tone of the voice of Twitter is more informative. By using emojis, we will increase the engagement of the audience and exchange of ideas.

LinkedIn profile: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/interstoreproject/>

LinkedIn is a Social Media channel used for professional networking related to business and professional activities. It will help the project to stay up-to-date on the industry trends, get feedback from peers, and build a strong connection and trusting relations with the target audience. The tone of voice is more formal, technical and focused on the topic.

The Social Media channels were created in January 2023. To improve the synergies among project partners a digital editorial plan is being designed to assure the contribution of the entire consortium. The first results of the editorial planning can be found in the [Appendix E](#).

2.4.1 Analysis of social media data and website

It is crucial to investigate and track Social Media activity and the performance of its results. EASE will provide WP6 partners with the analysis of the Social Media activities about the followers and content engagement within the audience. This activity can help to better understand the audience of the project and, based on that, to improve the content and adjust the communication strategy.

To measure the performance of the website, Google Analytics will be used to track the users, new users, views, amount of page views per unique visitor, engagement rate with different website pages, and via which channel the user arrived at the website (organic search, Social Media, backlinks etc.).

2.5 Newsletter

As per the Grant Agreement, a bi-annual newsletter will be sent out with news concerning the project's activities, key results, and future events related to the project. The audience data of the InterSTORE project will be on the Mailchimp platform. This platform will be used for email marketing campaigns and newsletters. The contacts will be collected directly from the website to the Mailchimp platform, and EASE will share the link with the embedded form with Consortium partners. The partner will cooperate and share this link with their internal contacts. The Secretariat of EASE is run by CLERENS NV/SA, which is the data controller, responsible for processing personal data in accordance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). For more details regarding the Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy, click [here](#)².

2.6 Leaflet, posters, roll-up

In the framework of the project, several printed materials will be designed and distributed to the partners, and more precisely:

1. a leaflet,
2. 5 posters (1 general + 4 for the pilot)
3. a roll-up

These documents will include general information about the project and will be designed for the non-expert's audience of relevant stakeholders.

EASE is currently (in June 2023) working on the development of these materials and collecting the information from the partners. These materials will be used for dissemination purposes during different events, meetings, and conferences and will be distributed to partners' organisations. All the materials will be designed respecting the visual identity of the project and will be printed in sufficient quantities for the duration of the project.

2.7 Scientific publications

The research and industrial partners will submit scientific articles to scientific journals and conferences to disseminate project outcomes and results. All the articles will be realised as Gold and Green Open Access peer-reviewed, namely they will be available directly from the publisher or in a website or repository. ZENODO <https://zenodo.org> was considered one of the most common repository for this scope, some verification has been made since it is based in

² <https://clerens.eu/privacy-cookie-policy/>

Switzerland. The final results of InterSTORE will be disseminated in high-impact journals such as Energies MDPI, Smart energy international, and IEEE Open Journal of the Industrial Electronics Society. The news about scientific publications will be widely promoted on Social Media channels and Website.

2.8 Media

EASE and other partners will help to disseminate different activities such as press releases, news reports, and scientific articles via their internal channels (newsletters, website, and social media promotion). All the press materials related to the InterSTORE project and the development of their activities will be published on the InterSTORE website and Social Media channels. In the framework of external events, in which Consortium partners will be present to raise the visibility of the project, communications and dissemination materials will be shared with the organisers and spread within their network. Press releases related to the important milestones (kick-off of the project, use cases updates, developments of the software, important European Commission events, etc.) will be regularly shared among the partners. The first press release was disseminated among consortium partners on their social media and websites (M1) (see the references).

2.9 Promotional Video

Two videos presenting the InterSTORE project will be developed. The first video will include general information about the project, its objectives, goals, timeline, and context.

The second video will focus on the development of the project's tasks and achievements, critical risks the Consortium partners encountered, and how the project could overcome these risks and achieve its goals. The exact content will be adapted to the Consortium's needs with the aim of reaching the general public.

The videos will be uploaded on the project's website, on Social Media channels, and disseminated within the partner's network. Viewers will be encouraged to like, share, and comment on the videos, extending their reach and engagement.

2.10 Events participation

To maximize the influence of the project and foster active involvement from a wide range of stakeholders, InterSTORE's partners will undertake shared responsibilities by actively participating in a diverse array of events. These events will serve as platforms to advocate for interoperable InterSTORE solutions that bolster decentralized storage systems across various domains. Events participation is an efficient way to engage with new stakeholders, raise awareness of the project and draw a solid network that will help with the dissemination of the results bringing new cooperation with similar projects and initiatives.

As a result, InterSTORE's partners, who have the obligation to attend different conferences, workshops, and seminars to disseminate the results and raise awareness of the project, will regularly fill in and update the list of events.

2.10.1 External events

The table below shows the list of potential events that Consortium partners can attend to disseminate the outcomes and results of the project. This list is available on the Sharepoint of the project, therefore each partner can access any time and contribute to it. The list is reviewed at monthly WP6 meetings.

Table 2: List of awareness-raising events

Name	Date	Place	Partners
BRIDGE Assembly	28/03/2023 – 30/03/2023	Brussels, Belgium	INESTEC
Hannover Messe	20/04/2023	Hannover Germany	VDE
Distribution Grids Fit for Tomorrow	05/04/2023	Webinar	All interested parties
ACER workshop on electricity storageE	11/05/2023	Ljubljana (Online)	All interested
Decarbonization standards in the steel sector – why, what and who?	15/05/2023	Stockholm / Online	All interested
Conclusions on Fit for 55: renewable heating and cooling solutions	17/05/2023	Webinar	All interested
Linux Foundation Energy Summit	01/06/23 – 02/06/23	Paris, France	RWTH
InterSOLAR EXPOs	13/06/2023 – 16/06/2023	Munich, Germany	CYG
Power Summit 2023	20/06/2023 – 21/06/2023	Brussels, Belgium	TBD
ENERGY LINUX SUMMIT	30/06/2023	Prague, Czechia	CYG
POLITICO Pro Workshop – The EU's battery regulation in the era of strategic autonomy	09/07/2023	Online	All interested
Energy Storage Global Conference	10/10/23 – 12/10/23	Brussels, Belgium	EASE, ENEL X
Battery Innovation Days	14/11/23 – 15/11/23	Bordeaux, France	EASE, ENEL X, others
9th Energy Storage Summit UK 2024	21/02/2024 – 22/02/2024	London	TBD
Lisbon Energy Summit	28/05/2024 – 30/05/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	TBD

2.10.2 Workshops, webinars and clustering activities

To reach the outcomes and maximise the results of the project, several workshops, webinars, and conferences will be organised by the Consortium partners in collaboration with other initiatives and EU-funded projects, such as: 2Zero, BRIGHT, PLATONE, Bridge and Linux Foundation Energy, InterConnect. By exploring synergies, the InterSTORE project will exchange knowledge related to sharing and valorisation of data spaces.

The InterSTORE's consortium is currently engaged in exploring and creating connections with two EU-funded projects, which are FlexCHESS: 'Flexibility services based on Connected and

interoperable Hybrid Energy Storage System' (for more info [here](#)) and PARMENIDES: 'Plug&play eneRgy ManagEmeNt for hybrID Energy Storage' (for more info [here](#)).

The table below illustrates the timeline and scope of activities suggested to be implemented in regard to the InterSTORE collaboration scheme:

Table 3: InterSTORE collaboration scheme timeline and activities

Timeline	Activities
Identification (May - June 2023)	The first step encompasses the identification of the projects funded under the HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01 call for proposals. Project partners will engage in identification of projects funded under the same call, thus responding to the same challenge. This phase resulted with excel file with the relevant contact and information about the collaborative projects.
Planning (July - August 2023)	After identifying and establishing the first contact, InterSTORE, FlexCHESS, and PARMENIDES will organize a joint online session in July 2023. The aim is to learn more on all the initiatives and spot the common grounds for cooperation. The dissemination leaders of projects will present the communication plans and recognize the potentials for mutual actions. First draft of the common action plan will be communicated between the projects.
Implementation (September 2023 - December 2025)	Following the design of the first collaboration action plan, projects will engage in implementation of envisaged efforts. Provisional activities from the communication viewpoint, might include common newsletter, sections on websites, participation on various events, etc. A physical meeting will be foreseen after Y2, where the main results will be shared among the three project partners.
Evaluation (November - December 2025)	Collaborative activities will take place until the end of the InterSTORE project. In the final stage, consortium will engage in the brief evaluation of the efforts undertaken in order to increase the knowledge in collaborative activities performance.

2.11 Final Event

To properly present the results of the InterSTORE project, EASE will organise the Final Event in Month 36, which will gather all stakeholders and provide the project's outputs and lessons learned. On that occasion, the partners will show the evidence to support the InterSTORE frameworks and toolkits. Its aim is to give EU Policy stakeholders, industry stakeholders,

industry, research communities and similar EU-funded projects the possibility to discuss the results, common challenges and solutions. The final event will be open to the general public, with the aim of involving a larger audience.

By organizing a Final Event that includes presentations, discussions, and networking opportunities, we will be able to effectively present the results of the InterSTORE project, facilitate knowledge exchange, and foster collaboration among stakeholders. This event will serve as a platform to showcase the project's outputs, engage with the audience, and stimulate further advancements in the field. The content and agenda of the final event will be elaborated during WP6 meetings with elaboration of all the partners.

3. INTERNAL COORDINATION AND PROCEDURES

As the leader of WP6, EASE plays a crucial role in coordinating InterSTORE's Communication and Dissemination activities. This includes content production, but also relies on the contributions from project partners based on their outreach and development of the tasks. EASE will be in charge of collecting and adapting the content provided by partners.

3.1 Content production and relevant procedures

Consortium partners, as previously mentioned, are committed to deliver the content for the website and Social Media of the project. The procedure will be as follows:

1. *Content produced by a partner*

- Partner sends the communication material to EASE;
- EASE will analysis whether it corresponds to the requirements and it is coherent with the C&D strategy;
- If the content is proper, EASE adapts if needed and publishes it.

The partner has the right to tag the InterSTORE project on Social Media and communicate the materials through its own Social Media channel.

2. *Content produced by an external source*

External content could be published on the website and Social Media. However, EASE, as the coordinator, will decide if the content could be published.

The procedure is the following:

- Partner has to note EASE that the content is external;
- Explain the purpose of publishing such content, and how it can contribute to the stakeholder engagement C&D objectives;
- If EASE finds it appropriate, it will be communicated with the coordinator for his approval.

3. *Interaction with media*

In case partners have the opportunity to speak about the project, EASE and all the partners shall provide all the necessary materials and support any procedure: leaflet, PowerPoint, and publications.

3.2 Internal Repository

All partners have access to the private internal repository SharePoint on Teams (see [Appendix F – Internal Repository](#)). All the files related to the activity of each Work Package will be located there. The partner EnelX is managing the platform and its access. All the partners will receive a regular update on the project's status, planning, or any other important issues. The platform is used to maintain transparency within the partners and make the consortium's work easier.

It was decided that WP leaders will hold on a monthly basis to monitor the progress of the development of the activities related to their tasks. The PowerPoint presentations of each meeting have to be uploaded in a dedicated folder on SharePoint in order to facilitate the exchange of information.

3.3 Dissemination procedures

In accordance with the Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement and the article 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement, beneficiaries are required to disseminate their results as soon as possible in a publicly available format, taking into account any applicable restrictions related to intellectual property protection, security rules, or legitimate interests.

The procedure for the publication of results is described by article 8.4.2.1 of the Consortium Agreement, which states as follows:

- Prior notice of any planned publication (including sufficient information concerning the planned Dissemination activity and the data envisaged to be disseminated) shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication;
- Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Beneficiary or Beneficiaries proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice on the planned publication;
- If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

3.4 Open Access

As per the Grant Agreement Article 1.2.6 'Open Science Implementation', scientific publications related to the results achieved within the project lifetime will be released as Gold and Green Open Access peer-reviewed.

InterSTORE aims to contribute to the EC policy and promotes openness, integrity, and reproducibility in the research and innovation approach. For this reason, InterSTORE partners will assure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results, by the modalities prescribed by Article 17 and the Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

The scientific publications will be stored on the online repository on SharePoint in a dedicated file.

4. PERFORMANCE ASSESMENT

To monitor the efficiency of the C&D activities and stakeholder engagement, a set of Key Performance Indicators was identified and will be overseen within the duration of the project. Every 6 months the results of the monitoring will be presented to the WP6 partners as well as to all Consortium during the General Assembly of a project.

4.1 Key Performance Indicators

The performance of the website will be monitored through Google Analytics. LinkedIn and Twitter have their own platform algorithms allowing the Communication Officer to track the evaluation directly on the platform. Table 3 below shows all KPIs for all the communication activities for the duration of the project.

Table 4: List of KPIs

Tool	Indicator	Target
Brochures	#brochures distributed	At least 200 per year
Posters	#poster produced	5 in total <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 general • 1 for pilot
E-Newsletter	#NL and # subscribers	2 per year 500 registered addresses
White Paper	#Industry, Standardization and Policy Makers reached	Top level standardized organization and at least 1 EU parliament and EU commissioner reached
Social Networks	#followers on LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube	>3500; >9000; >1000
Workshops/Webinars	#workshop and #of participants	4 workshops (100 parts/average)
Participation in conferences/events	#of events attended	>8 per year
Videos	#video and average, #views	2 videos and >500 views/Video
Scientific Publications	#peer-reviewed papers/articles	>10 by the end of the project
Website	#unique visitors	>1000/yr
Final meeting	#of participants	>300

4.2 Road Map

Figure 1: Road map

As elaborated in the section 3.1, all project partners have responsibility to provide the relevant content for the social media and website, and participate in other communication activities. In order to coordinate these actions, the consortium has created a plan of actions until the end of the ongoing calendar year (see picture above). More detailed planning will be presented for the upcoming year, through the Editorial plan 2024 to be developed in the upcoming months. This is aligned with the expectation to have more content available for dissemination, as the project evolves.

Until then, the communication material (including leaflet, newsletter, roll-up and poster) will be prepared by EASE and made available for the consortium to use. Considering that the project is at the starting phase there are not a lot of results and achievements to share, social media campaign will be launched during summer months of 2023, in order to present the project partners and their participation in the project. Provisional timeline for this campaign is presented in the table below.

Table 5: Actions timeline

Name of activity (example)	Content	Channel	Status of the content
Partner’s presentation (RWTH, Julich, EATON, VDE)	Description, how the partner is involved in the project, insight	LinkedIn	Work in progress, expected delivery July 2023
Partner’s presentation (EnelX, Engineering, Sunesis, CyberGrid)	Description, how the partner is involved in the project, insight	LinkedIn	Work in progress, expected delivery August 2023
Partner’s presentation (CapWatt, Inesctec, HESS, EASE)	Description, how the partner is involved in the project, insight	LinkedIn	Work in progress, expected delivery September 2023

4.2 Deliverables

The following table presents expected deliverables within the WP6 of the InterSTORE project.

Table 6: List of deliverables

Deliverable	Month Due	Responsible partner
D6.1 Report on project identity and website	M3	EASE
D6.2 First Communication and Dissemination Plan	M6	EASE
D6.3 First draft of the Exploitation Strategy, Plan and IPR report	M12	VDE
D6.4 Final Exploitation Roadmap including Business Plan and IPR Report	M32	RWTH
D6.5 Final Communication and Dissemination Plan	M32	EASE

4.3 Partners responsibility

The table below represents the Communication team responsible for the draft of this plan.

Table 7: Communication Team

Organisation	Main Communication Responsible	Support
EASE	Elizaveta KUZMINA	Clara CALVARUSO
EASE	Stefani KREČAR	

EASE is leading WP6 related to C&D activities of the InterSTORE project, and thus it is in charge of task 6.1 'Communication and Dissemination', which includes the development of the visual identity, preparation of different materials, official templates, project website and social media set up, printed materials: leaflets, posters, regular updates to the website and Social Media channels, reporting on evaluation of the results of the audience engagement, preparation of a bi-annual newsletter, and organisation of the workshops and public events.

EASE is also responsible for task 6.3 related to managing the stakeholder group, to increase the impact of the project and engage with more stakeholders with the help of all the partners, particularly INESC. The Consortium partners are required to participate in a variegated number of events to promote interoperable InterSTORE solutions to support decentralized storage systems in different domains.

Together with EnelX and all the partners, EASE indicated the targeting audience to maximise the impact of the project, and disseminate the results of the project and increase the visibility of the project.

VDE partner is the leader of task 6.2 related to Technology transfer to the DES manufacturer group. VDE, which collaborates with Sunesis, CyberGrid, RWTH, INESC TEC and Engineering, is committed to providing all related information to the WP6 partners monthly call.

EnelX is responsible for task 6.4 on exploitation activities and will develop a long-term R&D strategy beyond the project duration.

After the end of the project, RWTH together with EnelX, VDE, Engineering, and EASE will work on task 6.5 to ensure software maintenance by creating an active community. The partners

will make a deep analysis on how to maximise the economic impact of the solution including emerging innovative approaches to data monetization in the context of data spaces.

CONCLUSION

The deliverable 6.2 “First C&D Plan” provides a comprehensive plan for communication and dissemination activities related to the InterSTORE project. Its primary purpose is to establish a strategy that will maximize the project's impact, increase visibility, and effectively disseminate the project's results.

The First C&D Plan contains a detailed outline of the communication strategy, which includes a set of tools and methods that will be utilized to achieve the project's objectives. It also identifies the long-term goals and objectives of the project, determining the key target audiences. The plan explains how these goals will be accomplished, providing a roadmap for successful dissemination.

However, it is important to note that some of the content and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the plan may be subject to adaptation or change as the project progresses and its tasks evolve.

The implementation of this plan will be monitored and assessed through Deliverable 6.5, referred to as the "Final Communication and Dissemination Plan," which is scheduled to be completed in Month 36 of the project.

Appendixes

Appendix A - Project logo, colour scheme, typography, icons

Figure 2: Old logo

Figure 3: Updated logo

RGB

6 16 97	92 82 246	50 204 218
#061061	#5f52f6	#32ccda

Figure 4: Colour Palette

Bahnschrift

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Figure 5: Bahnschrift font

Arial

REGULAR ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 0123456789

BOLD **ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ**
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Figure 6: Arial font

N27

LIGHT ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 0123456789

MEDIUM **ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ**
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Figure 7: N27 font

Figure 8: Icons

Figure 9: Cubes

Appendix B – Templates

D#.# - Deliverable Title

Work Package Number - Work Package Name
 Task Number - Task Name
 Submission date of deliverable: Day Month Year

Project Acronym	INTERSTORE
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01
Grant Agreement N°	101096511
Project Start Date	01-01-2023
Project End Date	31-12-2025
Duration	36 months

Figure 10: Deliverable template

To Name Surname | Company | Code | Date

Dear Name,

[Text]

Sincerely,

Name Surname
 Company

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Figure 11: Letterhead Template

Figure 12: Presentation Template

Figure 13: Minutes Template

TITLE

REVISION INDEX

Date	Version	Author	Comment
DD-MM-YY	1.0		The first draft
	2.0		Updated version
	FINAL		Final and submitted version

Location: 00 Road 000, interstore

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- 1.1 SUBCHAPTER 2
- 1.1.1 Subtopic 2
- 1.2 SUBCHAPTER 2
- 1.2.1 Subtopic 2
- 2 CHAPTER 3
- 2.1 SUBCHAPTER 3
- 2.1.1 Topic 3
- 2.1.2 SUBCHAPTER 3
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Figure 14: Text Template

Appendix C – EU logo and appropriate text

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Figure 15: EU emblem

Appendix D – Sitemap

Figure 16: Sitemap

Appendix E – Articles

Enel X Website Publications:

- <https://corporate.enelx.com/en/media/press-releases/2023/05/with-enel-x-italy-participates-in-the-european-interstore-project-to-improve-the-efficiency-of-energy-storage-systems-0>
- <https://finanza.lastampa.it/News/2023/05/30/-interstore-enel-x-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-per-migliorare-efficienza-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-energia/MTQ1XzlwMjMtMDUtMzBfVExC>
- <https://finanza.repubblica.it/News/2023/05/30/interstore-enel-x-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-per-migliorare-efficienza-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-energia-145/>
- <https://www.industriaitaliana.it/sistemi-di-stoccaggio-energia-enel-x-progetto-europeo-interstore/>
- <https://ageei.eu/con-enel-x-litalia-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-interstore-per-migliorare-lefficienza-dei-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-di-energia/>
- <https://marketinsight.it/2023/05/30/enel-enel-x-partecipa-a-progetto-interstore-per-migliorare-lefficienza-dei-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-di-energia/>
- <https://www.exposave.com/con-enel-x-litalia-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-interstore-per-migliorare-lefficienza-dei-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-di-energia-29124>
- <https://ageei.eu/con-enel-x-litalia-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-interstore-per-migliorare-lefficienza-dei-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-di-energia/>
- <https://www.impresagreen.it/news/12462/con-enel-x-litalia-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-interstore-per-migliorare-lefficienza-dei-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-di-energia.html>
- https://www.borsaitaliana.it/borsa/notizie/radiocor/finanza/dettaglio/enel-partecipa-a-progetto-europeo-interstore-su-software-per-efficienza-stoccaggi-nRC_30052023_1536_418187907.html
- <https://energiaoltre.it/energia-enel-x-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-interstore/?v=16493213c8e175>
- <https://www.agenzianova.com/a/6480ca9a3508d3.96600654/4380749/2023-05-30/imprese-con-enel-x-l-italia-partecipa-al-progetto-europeo-interstore-per-migliorare-l-efficienza-dei-sistemi-di-stoccaggio-di-energia>
- <https://www.9colonne.it/413970/energia-con-enel-x-l-italia-partecipa-a-progetto-europeo-interstore-2>
- <https://www.cyber-grid.com/innovation-and-development/interstore>
- <https://www.eaton.com/gb/en-gb/company/news-insights/news-releases/2023/emea-interstore-consortium.html>

Appendix F – Internal Repository

Figure 16: Internal Repository

Figure 17: Scientific Publications file in the Internal Repository

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